

TEAPOTS: Agriculture Waste Pyrolysis and Thermocomposting for Renewable Energy in Sustainable Agri-Food Sector

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Agriculture represents a critical juncture of global energy consumption and environmental impact, with energy being essential across the entire value chain - from primary production to processing, drying, cooling, and storage.

Unfortunately, the heavy reliance on non-renewable energy sources increases the carbon footprint of the agricultural sector. The TEAPOTS Project addresses this by combining advanced technologies to convert agricultural waste into renewable energy, covering 100% of

electricity needs via pyrolysis units, Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) systems and refrigeration technologies supported by a Decision Support System (DSS). This innovative approach aims at reducing fossil-based energy reliance, thus lowering emissions from waste

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conditions. These pilots emphasize collaboration across the agricultural value chain, fostering partnerships among farmers, policymakers, industry players, and associations. A multi-actor approach will be employed to create a network of biomass producers interested in using agricultural waste to improve their environmental impact.

By transforming agricultural waste into valuable resources and enabling farmers for energy self-sufficiency, TEAPOTS aims at supporting the change to meet the European Union’s climate and energy targets for 2030 and its ambition of achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050, resulting in healthier ecosystems across Europe.

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burning and promoting a circular agricultural economy.

The innovative TEAPOTS Integrated Solution (TIS) transforms agricultural waste into valuable energy forms, such as heat, electricity, and refrigeration, while simultaneously producing biochar and compost as by-products. The first valorisation process employs pyrolysis to extract heat from waste, which is then converted into electricity using an ORC system. This electricity powers refrigeration for cold storage of agri-food products. The second valorisation process employs a Compost Heat Recovery System (CHRS) to generate hot water from biomass oxidation, which is suitable for sanitary applications. Together, these technologies deliver a modular and flexible solution capable of addressing seasonal and localized energy demands, enhancing sustainability, and reducing the use of synthetic fertilizers by repurposing biochar and compost as

biostimulants.

Both biochar and compost play a vital role in the TEAPOTS Project by enhancing soil health and promoting biodiversity. Biochar’s porous structure improves water retention and nutrient absorption in soils, while compost replenishes organic matter and mitigates soil compaction. These features can help reduce greenhouse gas emissions by up to 48% and combat soil erosion, reinforcing the transition to a sustainable, circular agricultural model. Mixed feedstocks in the TIS further optimize energy production and by-product quality, ensuring economic and environmental efficiency.

To support the efficiency of the TIS, it is paired with a significant digital component, the TEAPOTS Digital Platform (TDP), which utilizes satellite and field data to predict biomass growth and optimize logistics for agricultural waste management. This platform integrates operational data from the TIS to conduct life cycle assessments, evaluating environmental impact and overall system functionality. A data-driven Decision Support System (DSS) enables efficient planning for field operations and waste logistics, ensuring the continuous operation of the TIS throughout the different seasons. With a user-friendly interface, the TDP empowers end-users, particularly farmers, to actively manage their agricultural waste and energy production, transforming them into prosumers of renewable energy.

To ensure scalability, TEAPOTS solutions are tested and demonstrated through pilot implementation in two farms, one in Italy and one in Greece, designed to showcase the modularity and adaptability of the TIS under varying technical and environmental

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